

Job Satisfaction of Female IT Professional in Coimbatore District

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyses the level of job satisfaction among women employees of IT professionals along with the consideration of pay, work life policy etc. Six IT companies were selected by using purposive sampling method for the study. 100 respondents were selected randomly from six IT companies which are located in Coimbatore districts. The results indicate that above 60% of women employees are highly satisfied with their jobs. Job security is the most significant factor of job satisfaction of the employees of IT in Coimbatore district. Hence, the present study was undertaken to study the personal and socio-economic character of Female working in IT sector and to study the job satisfaction of IT women.

INTRODUCTION

Employment of women has increased qualitatively and quantitatively all over the world. As results of that bring out the women to take up employment in various fields. A recent trend seen in corporate world is the entry of more women in the workplace. The extend of job satisfaction among women is an important aspect of their work experience. Job satisfaction is influenced by both personal and job factor. It spread the good will of the organization. Job satisfaction reduces absenteeism, low staff turnover, higher productivity, reduction in conflict and complaint, punctuality and Better worked morale. In recent survey conducted in 2013 among the IT employees of India shows that, primary reason for an employee leaving the organization is job satisfaction, whereas for senior employee, monotony in the role. So employees satisfaction is very essential one, these there arise a need to study the Job satisfaction of IT women Professional. In order to understand the job

satisfaction among the IT women professional the present study was designed and carried out.

REVIEW OF LITRATURE

According Robert L kahn reveals, Job satisfaction does seem to reduce absence, turnover and perhaps accident rates’.

In Locke words Job satisfaction is defined as pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job or job experience.

Allen and et al also that the work and family conflict increased job satisfaction decreased among individual of both gender in diverse professions, various career stage and from different countries.

Objectives of study

To examine the Socio-economic condition of IT Female professional

To analyze the Job satisfaction of the IT Female professional

To know the work life policy of the IT Female professional

To identify the satisfaction for work life policy IT Female professional

METHODOLOGY

The research aims to study the Job satisfaction of IT professional among the female in the Coimbatore district of Tamil Nadu. For the purpose of the study 150 samples were selected through Snowball technique. The selected data has been arranged by using simple percentage method

ANALYSIS AND INTREPRETATION..

Table No: 1 Distribution of the respondents based on different characteristics

S,NO	CHARACTERICTICS	CATEGORY	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE %
1	AGE	25-35	51	34
		36-45	87	58
		45&above	12	8
2	EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION	BE	101	67
		ME	49	33
3	OCCUPATIONAL	Softwareengineer	46	31
		Program developer	25	17
		Design engineer	16	11
		System engineer	31	21
		Trainer	19	12
		coding engineer	13	8.
4	MONTHLY INCOME	10,000-30,000	36	23
		30,000-50,000	46	31
		50,000-70,000	25	17
		70,000-90,000	28	19
		Above 90,000	15	10
		Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

From the above table find 58 % of the respondents lie between the age group 36-45, 34% of them lie between the age group 25-35,8% are the above the age group of 45. 67% of them completed their under graduate degree and only 33% are their post graduate.31% of respondents are soft ware engineer, 21%System engineer17% are program engineer ,13 are trainer and 6% coding engineer. The major proportion of the respondents (31%) of them earns30, 000-50,000 per month, 23% are in 10000-30,000 and 10 % who earns above 90,000.

Table No2: Distribution of respondents based on their Work Environment

S,NO	CHARACTERICTICS	CATEGORY	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE %
1	Number of Year of service	Below5	23	15
		5-10	108	72
		Above10	19	13
2	Job satisfaction Level	Highly satisfied	92	61
		Satisfied	35	23
		Neutral options	18	12
		Disagree	3	3
		Strongly disagree	2	1
3	Provision of work life policy	Flexible hours	42	28
		Holidays/Paid time off	70	47
		Career Break	38	25

4	Satisfaction level for work life policy	Highly satisfied	60	43
		Satisfied	51	33
		Neutral options	26	16
		Disagree	10	6
		Strongly disagree	3	2
5	Job interest	Highly satisfied	53	35
		Satisfied	54	36
		Neutral options	24	16
		Disagree	13	9
		Strongly disagree	6	4
		Total	150	100

Source: Primary data

This table shows that 72 % of the respondents come under 5-10 year of service, 15% of the respondents comes under less than 5years of service. Nearly 61% of the employees are satisfied with the working conditions, 23% of the employees are highly satisfied with the working conditions, 12% of the employees have no idea and 1% of the employee is dissatisfied. Nearly 50% have holidays or paid time off , 28% have flexible hours for working in general and 25% have career break. 43 % of the respondents are highly satisfied with the work life policy ,34% of the respondents are satisfied with company policy of the respondents 16% are having neutral opinions and 2% of the respondents are highly disagree with the work life policy .36% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the job interest,16% of the respondents are having neutral opinions, 8%of the respondents are disagreeing with the job interest and 4% of the respondents are strongly disagreeing with the job interest

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of the study was drawn on the basis of the finding of the research study. Majority of the

Female professional in IT agreed that they were highly satisfied with their nature of work but they are less satisfied with work life policy and job interest.

The organization need to modify the work life policy of the employee , if there are given little more care ,the company can maintain good female worker with over all high level of satisfaction, organizational commitment and involvement . This will in turn lead to effectiveness and efficiency in their work which leads to increased productivity.

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